

Exploring the Association between Lister Training and Field Performance in 2020 U.S. Census Address Canvassing¹

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Abstract

The 2020 U.S. Decennial Census conducted an Address Canvassing field operation to update address lists. Prior to beginning field work, field staff received training and completed a training assessment pertinent to the operation. An assessment score was used to determine staff's mastery of knowledge and skills required for performing the field work. The purpose of the present study is to examine the association between assessment score and field performance. We constructed two binary field performance indicators based on quality control field data at the housing unit level: (i) a "critical" error (which results in coverage error), and (ii) any error (which may result in coverage error or other non-critical errors). We conducted Cochran-Armitage trend tests to explore the trend between performance errors and training assessment scores of field staff. Then, we repeated the trend tests on the four sub-domains of the assessment (knowledge, data entry, workflow, and navigation). The preliminary results reveal a significant trend of improved performance with an increase in assessment scores. Similar trends are also found for the sub-domains, with the knowledge domain showing the strongest trend.

Key Words: Decennial Census, field operations, training assessments, Cochran-Armitage trend test

1. Introduction

The first full-scale field operation of the 2020 US Decennial Census was the In-Field Address Canvassing operation, or IFAC. Census field workers, known as listers, carried out the 2020 IFAC operation by canvassing assigned areas with physical addresses throughout the US, comparing their observations on the ground with the Census Bureau's address list. Listers were trained in address listing procedures prior to canvassing, and used a laptop instrument to view address list information for their assigned areas while in the field. Upon completion of their training, listers followed procedures to canvass each assigned area and update the address list in their laptop instrument. For structures with living quarters or suspected to contain living quarters, listing procedures included: (i) verifying existing addresses if they required no change from what was shown on the address list; (ii) adding new addresses that were not yet on the address list; (iii) deleting addresses that no longer existed; and (iv) correcting addresses where any information was incorrect or out of date. Listers also added new streets and collected map spot locations for each address using latitude/longitude coordinates.

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The 2020 IFAC operation was conducted between August and October of 2019, prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. The operation employed over thirty-two thousand field listers, and canvassed over fifty-three million addresses in the US. (Lane et. al., 2022). The 2020 IFAC operational plan differed from address canvassing operations in previous US Decennial Censuses in that the 2020 plan contained a smaller workload of areas for in-field canvassing than before. For example, the 2010 Address Canvassing operation had an initial workload of nearly 145 million addresses, which were all assigned to in-person canvassing. However, for the 2020 Census the workload was divided between an In-Office Address Canvassing (IOAC) operation and the IFAC operation. The 2020 IOAC plan reduced the IFAC workload by identifying stable areas that would not require in-person canvassing (Richmond & Hanks, 2022).

Our research explores the association between listers' training and field performance in the 2020 IFAC operation. To provide more context for understanding our data and methodology in Section 2, we will first explain details about the 2020 IFAC listers' final training assessment (sub-section 1.1), followed by an overview of the 2020 IFAC Quality Control (QC) operation (sub-section 1.2). We use data from these sources to operationalize training and field performance, respectively.

1.1 2020 IFAC Lister Final Training Assessment

To prepare listers for the 2020 IFAC operation, all staff attended a combination of classroom and online training with a laptop instrument, and carried out field exercises. At the conclusion of training, all staff were required to complete a final assessment. This was an online test to evaluate listers' basic knowledge and performance of following correct procedures for address listing. The assessment consisted of fifteen questions – five of these were brief multiple-choice questions, with the first multiple-choice question shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 2020 IFAC Lister Final Assessment, Question 1 (multiple-choice question)

The remaining ten questions were longer multi-step field “scenario” questions. For each “scenario” question, a text description was provided for what a lister would observe in a given hypothetical situation with one or more addresses, and what information was already in their address list for these. The lister would then have to follow the correct sequence of steps in their test instrument to update these (fictional) addresses; the scenarios in these questions simulated actual field listing operations using a laptop instrument, as if they were dealing with real addresses in the field. The number of steps required to complete a given scenario question ranged from four to twenty-nine steps, depending on the details of the scenario designed in the question. Figure 2 below provides the first screen from one of these scenario questions.

Figure 2: 2020 IFAC Lister Final Assessment, Question 6, first screen (multi-step scenario question)

Each multiple-choice question, and each discrete step in a scenario question, was programmed as a scored item that could be answered or done either correctly or incorrectly. If the correct answer was selected for a multiple-choice question, or if the correct action was taken for a given step in a scenario question, the lister would receive a given point value, and proceed to the next item. If an incorrect answer was selected, or if an incorrect action was made, the lister would be presented a pop-up text screen stating this was incorrect and what the correct answer/action was before proceeding, and they would receive no points for the incorrect answer/action. In total, there were 167 scored items in the assessment between the fifteen questions, and these items were categorized into four types by the Census Bureau subject matter experts (SMEs) – these categories were named Knowledge, Data Entry, Workflow, and Navigation. The SMEs also determined the most appropriate point values for a correct answer/action to an item within each category, and provided justification for the scoring, in developing the final assessment (Tuttle et al., 2019):

1. *Knowledge items* were identified as the most important for listers, requiring correct application of fundamental subject matter knowledge related to classification and updating of structures. These items were thus awarded the highest weighted point value for a correct answer/action, at ten points each. Each of the five multiple choice-questions were categorized as Knowledge items, as were particular items in scenario questions, such as selecting the appropriate “Address Status” or “Structure Type” for a given address.
2. *Data Entry items* were also identified as important, requiring accurate entry of data related to structures such as address text and selecting map points. These items were awarded five points each for correct entry.
3. *Workflow items* were identified as relatively less important, requiring clicking of correct icons related to a given address while making updates. These items were awarded two points each for a correct action.
4. *Navigation items* were identified as the least important, requiring clicking of correct navigational buttons that do not involve judgments based on subject matter knowledge. These items were awarded the lowest point value of one point each for a correct action.

Between all of the items in the assessment, the maximum number of points a lister could receive was 773. This raw point total was normalized to a score between 0 and 100 percent. Listers who scored 70 percent or higher “passed” and could immediately begin field work. However, those who scored less than 70 percent required a mandatory observation period by a supervisor while in the field before they would begin listing on their own.

1.2 2020 IFAC Quality Control Operation

During the same period of production for the 2020 IFAC operation, which was between August and October of 2019, there was also a Quality Control (QC) operation to evaluate the work quality by field listers. For the QC operation, a sample of addresses canvassed during the production phase was canvassed again later by a different QC lister, and listing results were compared between the production and QC listers for each address.

The initial workload for each lister in 2020 IFAC production was divided into assigned areas, known as Basic Collection Units (BCUs) made up of one or more addresses. Later, a sample of these BCUs was selected for QC based on several criteria from the 2020 IFAC production listing results. These criteria were based on several “checks” for the BCU, such as meeting a set threshold of address types that are historically more prone to error, or meeting a threshold of physical distance between the lister and one or more addresses at the time of listing. For each check that met or surpassed a threshold, a set value of points was assigned. Each BCU was then given a total QC “sampling score” equal to the sum of these points, with each BCU assigned into one of three strata based on this score – named “High,” “Middle,” or “Low.” All BCUs in the High stratum were selected for QC; among BCUs in the Middle and Low strata, a sample of ten percent and five percent, respectively, was randomly selected for QC. Overall, the number of eligible BCUs selected for QC was 123,000, or 11.8 percent of the original workload (Roinestad et al., 2022).

Within each BCU selected for QC, the number of addresses assigned to QC depended on the total number of addresses in the BCU from the original production workload. BCUs with the smallest range of addresses (i.e., twenty or fewer) had all of their addresses assigned to QC, while BCUs with more addresses had a subset of these assigned to QC. Of the original 2020 IFAC address workload with over fifty-three million addresses, approximately 3.4 million eligible addresses were worked again in the QC operation. Also, about 84 percent of listers that worked at least one address in 2020 IFAC production received QC for some part of their workload (Roinestad et al., 2022).

For cases in which there were discrepancies between a production lister and QC lister at a given address, these were categorized into two error types. The more serious error of these two error types was called a “critical error,” which is a coverage related error. One example of a critical error would be a new address not on the address list that was missed by a production lister, but noticed and added by the QC lister. The less serious of these was called a “minor error,” which is not coverage related but may make finding an address more difficult. One example of a minor error would be a production lister listing an address status as “Housing Unit,” but a QC lister changing the status to “Under Construction.” Once QC was completed for a BCU, the BCU would “pass” QC if the number of critical errors fell below a minimum threshold, or “fail” QC if the threshold was reached. Of the BCUs worked in QC, the failure rate was 34.8 percent (Roinestad et al., 2022).

While analyzing the BCU-level QC failure rate is useful, this provides limited information about field performance and lacks specific details. For example, if data is provided for each BCU on whether or not they passed QC, this alone would not inform us of the specific types of errors (e.g., critical or minor) or how many occurred for either within each BCU. In addition, for each BCU selected for QC, the number of critical errors permitted to determine pass or failure depended on the number of addresses. For example, BCUs with a smaller number of addresses in production (e.g., seventy or fewer) would have twenty or fewer addresses selected for QC, and the BCU would fail QC based on a single critical error. However, BCUs with the highest number of addresses (e.g., more than 525) would have sixty-five addresses selected for QC, and the BCU would fail QC if there were more than three critical errors. For a more precise measurement of the association between training and field performance, we need to conduct our analysis at the address level.

2. Research Design

Our research builds on previous studies of the 2020 IFAC operation by analyzing QC error rates at the address level, rather than QC pass or failure rates at the BCU level. In particular, we aim to explore the association between training performance and field performance for this operation by comparing QC error rates with listers' scores on their final training assessments. First, we examine whether 2020 IFAC production listers with higher assessment scores had lower QC error rates than those with lower assessment scores. Second, we examine to what extent QC error rates varied by listers' sub-scores for each assessment item type – Knowledge, Data Entry, Workflow, and Navigation.

In the next sub-section (2.1) we provide an overview of our data sources. These are from: (i) the 2020 IFAC Lister Final Training Assessment, including overall score and sub-score data; and (ii) the 2020 IFAC QC operation, including QC error data at the address level. Then we explain our statistical methodology to carry out our analyses in the following sub-section (2.2), before presenting our results in Section 3.

2.1 Data Sources

Each lister who took the 2020 IFAC Final Training Assessment received a score from 0 to 100 percent. We obtained a dataset with these final scores for over 24,000 of the IFAC production listers. In addition, we obtained a more detailed dataset for these listers, indicating whether they answered correctly or incorrectly to each of the 167 scored items. Using this information, we derived sub-scores for each lister on the four assessment item types. For example, the assessment contained 42 Knowledge items, so we derived each lister's Knowledge sub-score by calculating the number of Knowledge items answered correctly, dividing this number by 42, and multiplying this figure by 100, to yield a normalized Knowledge sub-score between 0 and 100. The same was then applied to yield sub-scores for Data Entry, Workflow, and Navigation, based on the number of items for each of these task types. Both of these IFAC score datasets – providing overall scores and four sub-scores – contained a unique ID for each Lister, allowing linkage between datasets.

For the 2020 IFAC QC operation, we obtained a customized analysis file which included address-level data from the Census Listing and Mapping Instrument (LiMA). This dataset was restricted to addresses that were canvassed in both 2020 IFAC production and QC. The data contained several fields; a few of these were: (i) the unique ID of a lister that initially canvassed the address in production; (ii) the unique household ID; (iii) timestamp information from the production lister; and (iv) a field with distinct error codes, indicating whether the QC lister's update differed from the production lister and how this differed. There were over 150 unique error codes for characterizing a given address, depending on the exact type of discrepancy between the production and QC lister, and an address could have more than one of these error codes. Using this field and a supplemental codebook (describing each error code value and whether categorized as a critical error or minor error), we were able to derive three new binary variables for each address. These informed us whether or not a categorical error type was recorded at an address – a critical error, minor error, or either error type, with '1' indicating an error and '0' indicating no error for each of these variables.

Using the unique 2020 IFAC production lister ID, we linked the data sources for Final Training Assessment scores and for the QC operation. The goal was to yield an address-level dataset, providing the overall score and four sub-scores for the lister that initially canvassed the address, along with whether or not any of the categorical QC error types were recorded at the address. Cases were removed from analysis if the lister IDs could not be linked between datasets, if any score data was missing for a given lister, or if there were anomalies in the assessment score datasets for a given lister, such as discrepancies between the overall score data and the detailed assessment item-level data. This resulted in a final data file containing approximately 2.6 million addresses in the QC operation, which were first canvassed by over 18,000 IFAC production listers.

2.2 Methodology

For our research, we first present the distribution of address-level QC error rates by overall training assessment score, where the score pertains to the IFAC production lister that initially canvassed an address. We categorize addresses based on the final assessment score of the lister, dividing these into seven different ranges or “bins.” The first bin is for addresses canvassed by listers with scores less than 70% (and who would have thus received additional training or supervision). The other bins cover six different ranges of scores for addresses canvassed by listers scoring 70% or higher (and who would have thus conducted all field work independently without additional training or supervision). This starts with scores of at least 70% but less than 75%, and increases in five-point intervals, up to the maximum score range for those with scores of at least 95% (including perfect scores of 100%). For QC error rates, we consider two measures: (i) critical error, and (ii) either error (including critical or minor).

Next, we run Cochran-Armitage trend tests to explore whether there is a significant linear trend between IFAC lister score and QC error occurrence at each household. This test yields a “z-statistic,” which indicates a significant trend if the value falls above a critical value. The formula to yield this value is shown below in Figure 3 (Agresti, 2002, Section 5.3.5). This analysis is based on categorizing the addresses into the bins mentioned above based on lister score; the number of bins is the value “k.” Then we form a contingency table between these score bins (y) and a binary QC error variable (x), taking into account the number of cases in each cell of the table (n), and the observed response probabilities for opposing outcomes (p and q). We run these trend tests based on both critical error occurrence and “either” error occurrence. We then present the z-statistic for each test and the corresponding p-value, indicating whether we find a significant linear trend.

$$z = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k y_i (x_i - \bar{x})}{\sqrt{\bar{p}\bar{q} [\sum_{i=1}^k n_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2]}}$$

Figure 3: Formula for z-statistic, based on Cochran-Armitage trend test.

Finally, we repeat these analyses, but using each of the four sub-scores (Knowledge, Data Entry, Workflow, and Navigation) for a lister rather than the overall score. This begins with the distributions of address-level QC error rates by each sub-score, categorizing addresses based on the “bins” as before but where the bins now represent ranges for a given sub-score. Then we run Cochran-Armitage Trend tests to examine whether there is a significant linear trend in the QC error occurrence likelihood over IFAC lister sub-score.

3. Results

We divide our results into two parts – the first covers IFAC listers’ overall scores on their training assessment, and the association between these and address-level QC error occurrence. The second covers IFAC lister’ sub-scores on each of the four training assessment item types – Knowledge, Data Entry, Workflow, and Navigation – and the association between each sub-score and address-level QC error occurrence.

3.1 2020 IFAC Final Training Assessment: Overall Scores

Figure 4 below shows the distribution of the final training assessment scores for the listers in our analysis data file that canvassed any addresses and had any addresses checked again later in the QC operation. Of these approximately 18,500 listers, just 1.3 percent scored less than 70 and received some additional training or supervision. The most common range was for scores of at least 90 but less than 95, with about 42 percent of listers scoring in this range, and the median score was 91. Also, 17 percent of listers scored in the highest range, with a score of 95 or higher.

Figure 4: 2020 IFAC Lister Score Distribution, among listers with any addresses in QC operation, N = 18,500 listers.

3.1.1 QC Error Rates, by 2020 IFAC Lister Overall Scores

Figure 5 provides the percent of addresses with any QC errors, by IFAC lister score, among the 2.6 million addresses in our analysis file from the QC operation. Among addresses that were originally canvassed by listers in the lowest score range (below 70), 10.6 percent of these had a critical error, and 15.9 percent had either a critical or minor error. Note that these error rates are lower than for addresses canvassed by listers who scored at least 70 but below 75, or at least 75 but below 80. This result may have been driven in part by the “under 70” group receiving additional training or supervision, which may have helped their field performance relative to those who scored at least 70 or slightly above and did not receive this help. Due to potential bias in this lowest scoring group, we omit them from all of our remaining analyses.

With the exception of this lowest scoring group, we find that QC error rates were lower among addresses canvassed by listers with higher scores than by those with lower scores. Addresses worked by listers with the highest training score range (95 or higher) had the lowest QC error rates; 6.3 percent of these addresses had a critical error, and 9.9 percent had either a critical or minor error.

Figure 5: 2020 IFAC Address-Level QC Error Rates, by IFAC Production Lister Final Training Assessment Score, N = 2,602,000 addresses.

3.1.2 Trend Tests, between QC Error Rates and 2020 IFAC Lister Overall Scores

Table 1 summarizes the results from Cochran-Armitage Trend tests among listers who scored at least 70 or higher on their assessment. This reduces the number of “bins” from seven to six, so that addresses canvassed by a lister scoring at least 70 but less than 75 made up the first bin, and addresses canvassed by a lister scoring at least 95 or higher made up the last bin. This also slightly reduces the number of addresses from the previous figure.

Based on these two trend tests, we find a highly significant linear trend between QC error occurrence at the address level and IFAC lister assessment score. For occurrence of critical errors, or of either error (critical or minor), the z-statistic has a highly significant value; the statistic is negative since error frequency declined as assessment scores increased.

Table 1: Cochran-Armitage Trend Tests between Address-Level QC Error Occurrence and IFAC Production Lister Final Training Assessment Score (N=2,578,000 addresses)

Error Type	z-statistic	p-value
Critical error	-84.15	<0.01*
Either error	-89.23	<0.01*

3.2 2020 IFAC Final Training Assessment: Sub-scores by Item Type

Next, we consider IFAC lister sub-scores for each of the four item types in the final assessment. Figure 6 below provides the distribution of IFAC lister scores on the final training assessment, among the listers in our analysis file that canvassed any addresses and had any addresses checked again later in the QC operation, and that had an overall score of at least 70.

For the Knowledge items, which were awarded the highest point value, the median sub-score was 88 percent correct. Then for Data Entry items, which had the next highest point value, the median sub-score was 94. For Workflow items, the median sub-score was 90. And finally for the Navigation items, the median sub-score was nearly perfect with 98 percent correct, and very few listers scored below 90 percent correct for these items. Recall that this category was awarded the lowest point value, since the subject matter experts identified these items as the simplest and least important.

Figure 6: 2020 IFAC Sub-Score Distribution, among listers with any addresses in QC operation, N = 18,500 listers.

3.2.1 QC Error Rates, by 2020 IFAC Lister Sub-Scores

Now we consider the percent of units with any QC errors, by each IFAC lister sub-score, starting with the Knowledge sub-score shown in Figure 7. We find that the error occurrence rates are highest at addresses canvassed by listers with the lowest Knowledge sub-scores (below 70); among these addresses, 11.4 percent had a critical error, and 16.7 percent had either a critical or minor error. The rates decline for each increasing sub-score range. QC error rates are lowest among addresses canvassed by listers with the highest Knowledge sub-scores (at least 95 or higher); among these addresses, 6.6 percent had a critical error, and 10.5 percent had either a critical or minor error.

Figure 7: 2020 IFAC Address-Level QC Error Rates, by IFAC Production Lister Final Training Assessment Knowledge Sub-score, N = 2,578,000 addresses.

Next, we consider this distribution based on the Data Entry sub-score, shown in Figure 8. In this case, QC error rates are lowest at addresses canvassed by listers with the lowest sub-scores (below 70). While this finding is initially surprising, it should be noted that this group had less than a tenth of one percent of all housing units, since very few listers who scored 70 or higher overall had a Data Entry sub-score below 70. Thus, inferences for this group are not feasible based on limited data. With the exception of this group, we find that QC error rates steadily drop as the sub-score increases. The error rate for addresses in the “70 to 75 sub-score” group have the highest error rate, with 14.7 percent having a critical error and 22.5 percent having either a critical or minor error. These rates are roughly halved for addresses in the “95 to 100 sub-score” group, with 7.4 percent having a critical error and 11.6 percent having either a critical or minor error.

Figure 8: 2020 IFAC Address-Level QC Error Rates, by IFAC Production Lister Final Training Assessment Data Entry Sub-score, N = 2,578,000 addresses.

Third, we examine the distribution for the Workflow sub-score in Figure 9. Like Data Entry, the number of addresses in the “Less than 70 Sub-score” group was low - at just one percent of addresses in this case - since few listers who scored 70 or higher overall had a Workflow sub-score below 70. Otherwise, QC error rates are highest at addresses canvassed by listers scoring between 70-75, with 10.9 percent having a critical error and 16.6 percent having either a critical or minor error. The QC error rates are lowest among addresses canvassed by listers scoring between 95 and 100, with 7.7 percent having a critical error and 12.0 percent having either a critical or minor error. Overall, the differences between groups are more modest for Workflow sub-score than we saw for Data Entry sub-score.

Figure 9: 2020 IFAC Address-Level QC Error Rates, by IFAC Production Lister Final Training Assessment Workflow Sub-score, N = 2,578,000 addresses.

Finally, we examine the distribution for the Navigation sub-score in Figure 10. We find that QC error rates vary widely between addresses in any of the first five lister sub-score ranges, with no clear discernible pattern. However, less than two percent of addresses in our analysis were canvassed by a lister who scored below a 90 for the Navigation items, since very few listers had this sub-score below 90; this may account for noise in the data. When comparing just those addresses canvassed by listers who scored between 90-95 with those who scored 95 or higher, we see the higher scoring group had a lower QC error rate. The critical error rate drops from 9.5 percent to 8.1 percent, and the “either” error rate drops from 14.5 percent to 12.5 percent.

Figure 10: 2020 IFAC Address-Level QC Error Rates, by IFAC Production Lister Final Training Assessment Navigation Sub-score, N = 2,578,000 addresses.

3.2.2 Trend Tests, between QC Error Rates and 2020 IFAC Lister Item Sub-Scores

Table 2 summarizes the results from Cochran-Armitage Trend tests between QC error rates and assessment sub-scores, among listers who scored 70 or higher overall on their assessment. We find a highly significant linear trend between QC error occurrence at the address level and any of the IFAC lister training sub-scores. For both critical error occurrence, or “either” error occurrence, the z-statistic has a highly significant value; the statistic is again negative since error frequency declined as sub-scores increased.

While all of the trends are significant, we find that the strongest z-statistic belongs to the Knowledge sub-score, relative to the other categories. Recall that Knowledge was given the highest weighted point value. We also find that the z-statistics are less strong as we move down the table to categories that were given lower weighted point values, with Navigation’s z-statistic not as strong as the other categories, though all are still highly significant. This suggests that the decision by subject matter experts to weight the categories the way they did in terms of points was justified. Knowledge had the strongest linear trend, followed by Data Entry, then Workflow, then Navigation.

Table 2: Cochran-Armitage Trend Tests between Address-Level QC Error Occurrence and IFAC Production Lister Final Training Assessment Sub-Score (N=2,578,000 addresses)

<i>Error Type</i>	<i>Sub-score</i>	<i>z-statistic</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Critical error	Knowledge	-77.90	<0.01*
Critical error	Data Entry	-64.08	<0.01*
Critical error	Workflow	-32.90	<0.01*
Critical error	Navigation	-22.45	<0.01*
Either error	Knowledge	-83.85	<0.01*
Either error	Data Entry	-65.31	<0.01*
Either error	Workflow	-37.04	<0.01*
Either error	Navigation	-25.80	<0.01*

4. Discussion

Our research goal was to explore the association between lister training performance (final training assessment score) and lister field performance for the 2020 IFAC operation (QC error rates). We started by deriving binary measures of error at the address level, based on presence of a “critical” error or any error, and grouping addresses from the QC operation based on the final assessment score of the lister that first canvassed the address. Our results found that addresses canvassed by 2020 IFAC production listers with the highest scores, between 95-100 percent, had the lowest QC error rates, and this percent usually increased as scores decreased. The one exception to this finding, however, was for listers who scored below 70 percent. Our initial descriptive results found that addresses canvassed by these listers had lower QC error rates than those canvassed by listers with scores between 70-75 or 75-80. Since this lowest scoring group of listers received additional training or supervision that was not provided for those with slightly higher scores, this may have helped them to perform somewhat better than those who scored slightly above the minimum score of 70 needed to “pass” and conduct all work without supervision. After this group was excluded from analysis, we conducted Cochran-Armitage trend tests and found a highly significant linear trend between final assessment score and QC error occurrence. This bodes well for the training assessment, suggesting that overall the assessment score reflects a lister’s knowledge and understanding of field procedures from training.

We then repeated our analysis using the same binary measures of error at the address level, but grouping addresses by lister sub-scores on each of the four item types from the final assessment – Knowledge, Data Entry, Workflow, and Navigation. Based on the Cochran-Armitage trend tests

for each of these item types, we found a highly significant trend between any of these sub-scores and QC error occurrence, and addresses canvassed by listers with higher sub-scores on any of these items were associated with lower QC error occurrence. While all trend tests were highly significant, the strongest z-statistic was found when testing the trend for the Knowledge sub-score, followed by Data Entry, then Workflow, and finally Navigation. This bodes well for the design of the training assessment, suggesting that the allocation of more points to correct answers for Knowledge items was reasonable, since the percentage of Knowledge items answered correctly had the strongest association with field performance. The allocation of lower point values for Data Entry, then Workflow, and finally Navigation was also reasonable based on our findings.

One limitation of our analyses was that it was not feasible to test suitable models predicting QC error rate based on lister score or sub-score. Our preliminary analyses (not presented in this paper) included logistic regression models predicting the likelihood of address-level QC error based on lister score/sub-score as well as additional predictors. Other analyses included linear regression models predicting a lister's QC error rate for all of their workload sent to QC, based on lister score/sub-score. However, these models were omitted due to weak fit between the variables, and we instead selected the Cochran-Armitage trend test. Although the findings bode well and convey that higher scores are associated with lower QC error rates, we cannot say whether assessment score predicts QC error likelihood, and we cannot say anything about causality in this paper.

Another limitation is that our methodology did not distinguish between addresses from different QC sampling strata, or study the relationship between this and lister score. For example, we did not determine whether listers with lower scores had a higher proportion of their workload selected for QC than listers with higher scores. Also, we did not determine whether those with lower scores were more likely to have a higher QC sampling score for their BCUs, based on either the types of units they worked or their physical distance from addresses. Our methodology considered all addresses that were in 2020 IFAC production and QC operations, grouping all of these together. It is possible that when controlling for these factors, the results may vary somewhat from what we present in this paper.

There are many possibilities to expand on this analysis to help guide the training and scoring for future Census operations that could be done with the training score data alone, without the addition of QC operational data. Another future direction is to conduct psychometric analyses to improve assessment scoring strategies. Findings from these analyses could inform revised point values for different items, or revised groupings of items, and also take item difficulty into account.

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